

Method -III: The dye combination was also separated on an alumina column of pH 10.6, (8 g ; 5 cm). After 2 hr, the mixed chromatogram was eluted with NaCl (10^{-3} M) and EV could pass out of the column with 40 ml of the eluent. On further irrigation with 20 ml of *n*-butanol-ethanol-water (1 : 1 : 2, v/v), the retained dye (JR) was eluted out.

It may, therefore, be said that alumina, after chemical pretreatment, can be converted into an useful chromatographic material, which, of course, needs a close adsorption-desorption study of the solutes.

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Utilization of Lime Dust and Lime Sludge— An Industrial Waste

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INDUSTRIES offer a number of bye-products and waste materials which can be utilized for useful purposes. Amongst the various wastes produced in a steel plant, lime dust and lime sludge have been studied in the present investigation. It is estimated that about 2000 metric tons of the above two waste materials are available every year from Rourkela Steel Plant alone. During the process of production of lime from the lime calcining plant, lots of lime fines below 5 mm size, commonly known as lime dust are produced. Lime sludge is obtained when calcium carbide is treated with water for the manufacture of acetylene gas. Both lime dust and lime sludge are waste materials as far as a steel plant is

concerned. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study whether these can be utilized for producing bleaching powder and gypsum, thereby conserving lime stone deposits for better use in cement and steel industries¹. Further, the utilization of these wastes will also increase the overall economy of the steel production.

Experimental

Preparation of bleaching powder : Experiments were planned to prepare bleaching powder from lime dust and lime sludge. Since lime sludge is moist, it was dried before use. The amount of CaCO_3 present in the sludge sample was negligibly small (nearly 1%) and hence prior ignition was not necessary. An adequate amount of the dried sample was taken in a conical flask and chlorine gas was passed over it with constant stirring. The formation of bleaching powder from lime and chlorine is an exothermic process and so the temperature was maintained constant round about 35° by circulating cold water round the reaction vessel. The reaction was complete in 30-40 min.

Fig. Flow sheet-preparation of bleaching powder.

The amount of available chlorine was estimated from a small amount of the sample each time following the standard method². The estimations were repeated at 15 days intervals for a period of 3 months to ascertain the storage capacity. The above experiments on preparation of bleaching powder and testing were carried out using other lime sources like sea shell lime, natural clinkers, and impure and low grade lime stone mineral available in Ganjam district of Orissa. The results are reported in Tables 1-3.

Preparation of gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) : Lime wastes can be converted into gypsum either by treatment with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ or by treatment with dil H_2SO_4 .

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT LIME SOURCES

Constituent	Lime dust	Lime sludge	Sea shell lime	Natural clinker	
				No. 1	No. 2
CaO	80.0	56.6	62.2	57.5	56.8
SiO ₂	1.8	4.6	0.8	5.5	12.8
Al ₂ O ₃	1.5	Traces	Traces	Traces	Traces
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.5	2.0	nil	6.7	5.0
MgO	2.5	0.8	2.0	1.0	1.0
Loss on ignition	8.2	33.0	34.2	27.6	24.0

NOTES

TABLE 2—FORMATION OF BLEACHING POWDER AT DIFFERENT INTERVALS OF TIME

Time of passing Cl ₂ (min)	% available chlorine in the bleaching powder samples				
	Lime dust	Lime sludge	Sea shell lime	Natural clinker	
				No. 1	No. 2
20	21.3	18.2	19.1	19.6	19.1
25	29.1	21.8	22.7	23.6	22.7
30	37.6	25.5	28.2	28.7	26.4
35	40.8	31.2	34.6	35.9	33.4
40	40.8	32.8	34.6	36.2	33.4

TABLE 3—STORAGE TEST AT DIFFERENT INTERVALS OF STORING

Period of storage (days)	% available chlorine in the bleaching powder samples				
	Lime dust	Lime sludge	Sea shell lime	Natural clinker	
				No. 1	No. 2
15	38.6	31.2	33.4	35.5	31.2
30	35.8	29.6	31.9	32.4	29.6
45	34.4	28.4	30.5	30.8	28.4
60	32.4	26.4	29.1	29.2	26.4
75	31.1	24.3	28.7	28.4	25.6
90	30.8	23.0	27.4	26.4	23.8

Treatment with (NH₄)₂SO₄: An aqueous suspension of a lime sample was taken in a beaker and (NH₄)₂SO₄ in stoichiometric ratio was added. The mixture was digested over a water bath for 2 hr. Calcium sulphate separated out due to its poor solubility which was filtered and dried at room temperature. It was found to contain 2 moles of water of crystallization.

Treatment with dil H₂SO₄: An aliquot of lime waste was treated with a slightly less than the required amount of dil H₂SO₄. The resulting solution was concentrated and crystallized. CaSO₄·2H₂O was obtained in a pure and dry state.

Discussion

Bleaching powder is related to the hypochlorites. It is formed when slaked (but otherwise dry) lime is treated with gaseous chlorine. From phase rule, microscopic³ and X-ray studies it was found that in the initial stages, a mixture of basic hypochlorite, Ca(OCl)₂·2Ca(OH)₂ and basic chloride, CaCl₂·Ca(OH)₂·H₂O was formed. By further chlorination the basic hypochlorite was converted to a normal

hypochlorite, Ca(OCl)₂. Ordinary bleaching powder consists of this normal hypochlorite and the basic chloride and this is a stable substance and non-deliquescent³. Temperature control is essential because the reaction is exothermic (evolving 477 Btu per pound of chlorine). Cooling is necessary during formation, otherwise the temperature will exceed transition temperature of 42° where it becomes less stable and more corrosive. X-ray examination shows various species above the transition temperature, which do not contribute to its utility⁴.

Since bleaching powder decomposes in presence of moisture, it offers storing problems. Usually it is mixed with free lime and stored. The added quick lime serves the purpose of absorbing free water and also the liberated chlorine so that the loss of chlorine on storing is minimum. In the present investigation, it was found that after storing for 3 months the loss of available chlorine is not more than 20-25% (Table 3). It was also noticed that gypsum was quantitatively prepared in a fairly pure condition from lime wastes by treatment with (NH₄)₂SO₄.

Both bleaching powder and gypsum have great utility in industry. Gypsum is used for making gypsum-board, plaster of paris and also in cement industry. Bleaching powder is used as a disinfectant and as a chlorinating agent in water treatment. Rourkela Steel Plant alone requires nearly 250 tons of bleaching powder per year and is now purchasing it @ Rs. 2,500/- per tonne. The lime wastes are now simply dumped spending Rs. 25/- per tonne. If these lime wastes are converted into bleaching powder and gypsum by known methods, it will not only increase the overall economy but also good lime stone deposits can be conserved for better purposes.

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